

The Change of Absorbance, Transmission, and Reflection Due to the Change of Concentration of $\text{Ag}_x \text{Co}_{(1-x)} \text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$

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Abstract— Five samples of $\text{Ag}_x\text{Co}_{(1-x)} \text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$ with concentrations $x=0.1,0.3,0.5,0.7,0.9$ were prepared. some optical properti of them were investigated. The crystal structure was found with the aid of XRD technique indicating that the crystal nano spacing decreases upon increasing the Ag concentration x and decreasing the concentration of Co. The results of the UV-VIS spectrometer indicated that the absorbance increases upon increasing the Ag concentration and decreasing the Co concentration. The transmission decreases when the Ag concentration increases associated with the decrease of Co concentration. The results of FTIR indicated that the transmission to Infrared radiation increases as the Ag concentration decreases and the Co concentration increases.

Keywords— nano, cobalt, silver, energy gap, absorption coefficient, diode.

I. INTRODUCTION

Atoms are the building blocks of matter.

Matter that is formed from a large number of atoms or molecules. The behavior of individual atoms can be described using the laws of quantum mechanics. The behavior includes optical, electrical, magnetic and mechanical properties. These physical properties of matter are used widely in electronic and energy generation. The widely spread applications is in energy generation and electronics

The optical properties like scattering, absorption, transmission, and reflection are directly related to the performance of electronic and energy devices [1,2]. The optical properties are related directly to the electron transitions between energy levels or energy bands [3,4,5]. The absorption and emission processes that result from electrons' transition between energy levels and bands are related directly to the reflection and refraction processes [6,7,8]. Thus, any changes of the energy levels or band structure can change the optical properties of matter [9,10,11]. But the change of the optical for bulk matter to satisfy the required needs is a formidable task. This requires searching for a new approach. This new approach is now called nanoscience [12].

Nanoscience is concerned with the study, of nano materials which are in the form of a very large number of isolated particles having dimensions ranging from one nanometre up to three hundred nanometres.

Nanomaterials can not obey classical laws but can obey quantum mechanical laws [13]. Changing the nano size, geometry, chemical composition, and concentration can change the physical properties of the nanomaterial. This results from the fact that changing these properties results from the changes of the band structure and the atomic bands according to the quantum laws [14].

Optical sensors and solar cells' performance is dependent mainly on the optical properties of matter.

Solar cells are now widely used since they convert solar energy to electricity. The commercially available cells are silicon cells which have lower efficiency and are expensive having complex fabrication processes. This forces scientists to search for new cell types [15]. Nano-solar cells are the best candidate [16]. Different nano cells were fabricated like polymer cells, zinc and copper oxide cells [17].

Many attempts were made to account for the factors controlling the absorption coefficient, transmission, and reflection. One of them was tackled by Zoa-noon who proposed a theoretical model using quantum laws and semi-classical laws to describe theoretically some empirical optical properties of thin films nano materials. The model succeeded in describing the effects of changing nano size on the absorption coefficient, refractive index, conductivity, and magnetic permeability [18].

The work of George G. Njema [19], is concerned with the deposition techniques, evaporation rate, type of solvents, and temperature. These factors were shown to have significant effects on the degree of crystallization. This in turn affects the absorption coefficient which increases upon increasing the crystallization degree.

In the work done by M.Schnaiter et al [20]., the results obtained found that the absorption coefficient is dependent on the wavelength. The absorption coefficient decreases when increasing the wavelength for large wavelengths. The work of Giorgio Dall'Olmo, et al [21] indicated that in the surface open ocean the absorption coefficient of chromophoric dissolved organic matter decreases upon increasing wavelength in the range (400-950nm). Herve Claustre et al [22] studied phytoplankton, nonalgal particles, and dissolved organic matter in coastal waters around Europe. They found that the absorption coefficient decreases when the wavelength increases in the range (400-750nm). Anette, Karlsson, et al indicated that the absorption coefficient decreases when the wavelength increases for mechanical pulps [23]. The work done by Ernesto, et al indicated that the increase of carbon concentration causes the atmospheric absorption coefficient of light to increase also [24]. The results of E. Weingartner, et al [25] indicated also that the increasing the wave length decreases the absorption coefficient for soot particles.

Ahmed A. A. et al [26] work is concerned with studying the properties of thin films formed when ZnS was doped with Al. The results indicated that changing Al concentration changes the absorption coefficient. The same samples were studied by M. H. Eisa et al [27] to show that the ZnAl is in the form of nano

particles. The morphology of these samples was tackled by Ahmed and others [28]. The results indicate the change of the roughness is associated with the change of AL concentration. Such roughness affects the absorption coefficient. All these attempts encourage us to do this work concerning Ag Co thin films. Section 2 is devoted for materials and methods while section 3 is concerned with the results. Discussion and conclusion are exhibited in sections 4 and 5 respectively.

II. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

High purities of silver nitrate [$\text{Ag}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ (96%)], Copper nitrate hexahydrate Cobalt nitrate hexahydrate [$\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (99%)], Iron nitrate [$\text{Fe}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ (98%)] and Nitric Acid (HNO_3 , 99%) were used as raw materials. All materials were reagent graded and distilled water was used in the preparation process.

Figure. 1 PH Meter and Sensitive plans images

Figure. 2 image of furnace Vulcan.

Five samples of $Ag_x Co_{(1-x)} Fe_2O_4$ were prepared in different concentrations using sol-gel method. The amount of metal nitrates in distilled water was homogenized and separation of metal ions were achieved by the use of sodium hydroxide. A required amount of nitric acid was added into the solution in order to modify pH value to be less than 5. The solution was constantly stirred and heated at $80^\circ C$ in a magnetic stirrer for an hour to condense into a gel. The obtained sol was then kept for 24 hours at room temperature to avoid reverse interactions, the samples were dried at $300^\circ C$ for 3 hours to get powder. Then, the obtained powders were grained by agate mortar and finally sintered at $750^\circ C$ for 4 h in a programmable furnace to remove any organic material present in samples. The final products were characterized using X-ray diffraction (XRD), and UV-VIS spectrometer.

Compounds ($Ag_x Co_{1-x} Fe_2 O_4$) were prepared using the gel-sol method at the concentrations shown. The study was carried out using XRD technology, through which its crystalline and nanostructure, its lattice parameters, and the locations of atoms inside the cell were determined.

Ultraviolet-visible radiation was used to evaluate the band gap and optical and electrical properties.

The type of chemical bonds within atoms was determined using FTIR.

The results of the studies were recorded in tables and presented graphically.

III.RESULTS

In this chapter the results of an examination of samples ($Ag_x Co_{1-x} Fe_2 O_4$) (0.1,0.3,0.5,0.7, and 0.9) are exhibited. X-ray diffraction (XRD) data have been recorded and displayed graphically using the Rietveld method to study their crystal nanostructure, lattice parameters, and the positions of atoms within the cell. The UV-visible is used to evaluate the band gap and optical properties beside electrical and magnetic properties using (FTIR) absorption spectra beside a special computer program

A. X-ray diffraction results ($Ag_x Co_{1-x} Fe_2 O_4$)(0.1 ,0.3,0.5 ,0.7 and 0.9)

TABLE I
LATTICE PARAMETERS OF $Ag_x Co_{1-x} Fe_2 O_4$ SAMPLES AT DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS

XRD Data	$Ag_{0.1}Co_{0.9}Fe_2O_4$	$Ag_{0.3}Co_{0.7}Fe_2O_4$	$Ag_{0.5}Co_{0.5}Fe_2O_4$	$Ag_{0.7}Co_{0.3}Fe_2O_4$	$Ag_{0.9}Co_{0.1}Fe_2O_4$
Space Group	C12/c1(15)	C12/c1(15)	C12/c1(15)	C12/c1(15)	C12/c1(15)
Crystal System	Monoclinic	Monoclinic	Monoclinic	Monoclinic	Monoclinic
Cell Parameters 10^{-10} m	a	11.7846	11.7846	11.7846	11.7846
	b	12.8314	12.8314	12.8314	12.8314
	c	6.8064	6.8064	6.8064	6.8064
Density ($g.cm^{-3}$)	5.503	5.519	5.525	5.532	5.541
Volume (10^{-10}) ³	960.846	960.839	960.832	960.824	960.819
d (10^{-10} m)	2.7265	2.7253	2.7245	2.7237	2.7231

Cell Angle	alpha	90	90	90	90	90
	beta	111.001	111.001	111.001	111.001	111.001
	gamma	90	90	90	90	90

B. UV-VIS Optical Results of ($\text{Ag}_x\text{Co}_{1-x}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$) samples:

Fig. 3 Relation between absorbance and wavelengths of five ($\text{Ag}_x\text{Co}_{1-x}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$)

Fig. 4 Relation between transmission and wavelengths of five ($\text{Ag}_x\text{Co}_{1-x}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$) samples (0.1,0.3,0.5,0.7 and 0.9)

Fig. 5 relation between reflection and wavelengths of five ($\text{Ag}_x\text{Co}_{1-x}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$) samples (0.1 ,0.3 ,0.5 ,0.7 and 0.9) Molar concentrations

C. FTIR Results of ($\text{Ag}_x\text{Co}_{1-x}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$) (0.1 ,0.3 ,0.5 ,0.7 and 0.9)

TABLE II
DATA OF IR SPECTRUM FOR $\text{Ag}_x\text{Co}_{1-x}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$ SAMPLES

No	Peaks (cm^{-1})	Bonds	Functional Groups
1	520	C–Br stretch	alkyl halides
2	1130	C–N stretch	aliphatic amines
3	1420	C–C stretch (in–ring)	Aromatics
4	1630	N–H bend	1° amines
5	1700	C=O stretch	α , β unsaturated aldehydes, ketones
6	3050	C–H stretch	Aromatics

Fig. 6 IR spectrum of $\text{Ag}_x\text{Co}_{1-x}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$ samples

IV. DISCUSS

The results showed the absorbance, transmission, and reflection of $(\text{Ag}_x\text{Co}_{(1-x)}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4)$ for the molar concentrations $x = 0.1, 0.3, 0.5, 0.7, 0.9$ are exhibited. The results of the XRD technique indicated that the crystal nano spacing d decreases upon increasing the molar concentration x .

The UV-VIS spectrometer foundations in Figure (3) indicated that the absorbance increases upon increasing the concentration of Ag and decreasing the concentration of Co. Figure (4) indicated that the transmission decreases as the Ag concentration increases associated with increase of Co concentration. The results of Figure (5) showed that the reflection in most cases for very long and very short-wave lengths increases when the concentration of Ag increase associated with an increase in Co concentration, as shown in Figure (5). The results of FTIR shown in Figure (6) indicated that the transmission to infrared radiation decreases as the Ag concentration increases.

The work done by many researchers confirms the results obtained. The results of Zoalnoon [18] agrees with our results since it indicates that the nano size change which is related to the concentration change changes absorbance. The work of Njema [19] indicated that evaporation rate and temperature which cause the concentration to change affected the crystallization rate which in turn affected the absence. Ernesto's results [24] confirm the work for showing that increasing the concentration of carbon increases the absorbance. Ahmed foundations [26,27] also indicated that changing Al concentration changes the absorbance.

The results obtained for the optical properties of $(\text{Ag}_x\text{Co}_{(1-x)}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4)$ indicated that the crystal spacing and transmission of infrared radiation decrease upon increasing the concentration of Ag and decreasing the concentration of Co. However the absorbance and reflection increase when the Ag concentration is increased and associated with the decrease in Co concentration.

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